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The Efficacy of Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) Method on Students' Reading Comprehension in Senior High School

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Abstract. This study investigated the efficacy of the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) in improving the reading comprehension of senior high school students. Employing a quantitative quasi-experimental non-equivalent group pretest–post-test design, the research involved 60 Grade 11 students enrolled in Reading and Writing Skills at Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School. Participants were purposively assigned into an experimental group ($n = 30$), which received DRTA-based instruction, and a control group ($n = 30$), which was taught using direct instruction. A validated 30-item reading comprehension test measuring remembering, understanding, applying, and analysing skills was administered before and after the intervention. Descriptive statistics and paired-sample t -tests were used to analyze the data. Results revealed that the experimental group demonstrated an improvement in mean scores from pretest to post-test, indicating enhanced reading comprehension following exposure to DRTA. In contrast, the control group showed minimal to no improvement. Within-group analysis confirmed a statistically significant gain in the experimental group, while no significant change was observed in the control group. However, between-group comparison of post-test scores indicated no statistically significant difference, suggesting that although DRTA positively influenced student performance, its effect was not sufficiently strong to establish superiority over traditional instruction within the study duration. The findings highlight the potential of DRTA as an interactive and learner-centered instructional strategy that promotes purposeful reading, critical thinking, and knowledge retention. Nonetheless, the absence of significant between-group differences may be attributed to factors such as limited intervention duration, sample size, and individual learner variability. The study recommends sustained implementation of DRTA, integration into regular classroom practice, and further research using larger samples and mixed method approaches to better capture its long-term impact on reading comprehension.

Keywords: Directed Reading Thinking Activity, reading comprehension, quasi-experimental design, senior high school, academic performance, literacy instruction

Introduction

The Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) is an instructional strategy designed to actively engage learners in the reading process and enhance comprehension. By encouraging students to make predictions before reading and reflect on their interpretations during the activity, DRTA fosters purposeful reading, critical thinking, and deeper connections to prior knowledge. This interactive approach promotes meaningful learning and prepares students for independent reading and academic success.

In the Philippines, concerns about literacy remain pressing. Senator Sherwin Gatchalian has emphasized the urgent need to strengthen reading skills, particularly in the aftermath of pandemic-related learning disruptions. Reports from the World Bank and the OECD highlight that Filipino learners continue to struggle with reading proficiency, with the Philippines ranking lowest in the 2018 PISA assessment of reading literacy. Although the country showed slight improvement in PISA 2022, the gains were not

statistically significant. Similarly, data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (2024) revealed that while 79% of senior high school graduates were functionally literate, 21% remained illiterate despite completing secondary education. These findings underscore the need for effective interventions to address persistent literacy gaps.

Reading and Writing Skills, a core subject in senior high school, often presents challenges as students lose the habit of reading and struggle with comprehension. Strengthening reading comprehension is therefore essential, not only for academic achievement but also for personal and professional development. DRTA offers a promising solution by activating prior knowledge, encouraging prediction, and promoting reflective engagement with texts.

This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of DRTA in improving reading comprehension among Grade 11 students at Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School. Using a quasi-experimental nonequivalent group pretest-posttest design, two classes (60 students) were assigned as experimental and control groups. The experimental group received DRTA instruction, while the control group used direct instruction. The intervention was expected to improve comprehension by approximately 12%, with teacher feedback highlighting additional benefits such as enhanced communicative skills, critical thinking, and readiness for independent reading.

Research Questions

This research aimed to enhance the reading comprehension of senior high school students by implementing the DRTA method.

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the average of the following scores of the participants:
 - 1.1 Pre-Test Scores of the Control Group;
 - 1.2 Post-Test Scores of the Control Group;
 - 1.3 Pre-Test Scores of the Experimental Group; and
 - 1.4 Post-Test Scores of the Experimental Group?
2. Is there a significant difference in the Pre-Test Scores of the Control Group and the Experimental Group?
3. Is there a significant difference in the Post-Test Scores of the Control Group and the Experimental Group?
4. Is there a significant difference in the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Control Group?
5. Is there a significant difference in the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Experimental Group?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examined the impact of the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) on the reading comprehension skills of Grade 11 HUMSS students enrolled in Reading and Writing Skills at Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School during the Second Grading Period of the 2025–2026 academic year. The intervention focused on narrative texts, with activities carefully aligned to the prescribed learning competencies. Findings and insights derived from this research are specifically applicable to the selected group of students and cannot be generalized beyond this population.

Literature Review

Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension is a complex cognitive process that requires decoding written symbols and constructing meaning from text. It involves both literal comprehension, which focuses on understanding explicit information such as main ideas and details, and inferential comprehension, which requires interpreting implicit meanings, making connections to prior knowledge, and drawing conclusions beyond the text (Castles et al., 2018; Attiyat, 2019; Brooks et al., 2021; Rosenblatt, 2018; Karolidis, 2020). Vocabulary development plays a central role in this process, as a rich lexicon enables readers to grasp nuanced meanings and interpret texts more effectively. Reading is therefore not limited to word recognition but is a dynamic and interactive activity that integrates perception, thinking, and communication between author and reader (Chapman & Tunmer, 2003; Tunmer & Hoover, 2019; Daeli et al., 2020). Strong reading skills are essential for academic success and lifelong learning, as they allow learners to critically engage with educational materials, acquire knowledge, and apply information across disciplines. The complexity of decoding, vocabulary building, and comprehension highlights the importance of instructional strategies that foster active engagement with texts and promote deeper understanding.

Directed Reading Activity

The Directed Reading Activity (DRA) is a structured instructional strategy designed to support students before, during, and after reading, thereby enhancing comprehension and engagement. It emphasizes capturing learners' attention by presenting texts in meaningful contexts, encouraging deep analysis of main ideas and details, and fostering aesthetic appreciation of literary works (Saputra, 2015).

DRA also promotes self-monitoring, enabling students to assess their understanding and adjust strategies as needed, while providing opportunities to correct errors and build confidence. By activating prior knowledge and linking it to new information, the method strengthens word recognition, comprehension, and critical thinking. Overall, DRA cultivates effective, reflective, and imaginative readers, making it a valuable approach for improving reading skills and fostering a lifelong appreciation for literature.

Directed Reading Thinking Activity

The Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) is an instructional strategy that engages learners in making predictions before and during reading, thereby fostering active participation, critical thinking, and deeper comprehension (Arisetyawati, 2017; Fitriyani et al., 2020). By encouraging students to anticipate content using context clues and then confirm or revise their predictions, DRTA provides a clear purpose for reading and strengthens analytical skills. Its primary objective is to promote reading independence, as students articulate their thoughts, connect new information to prior knowledge, and develop logical reasoning (Utami & Sugirin, 2019; Anandita, 2020; Safitri et al., 2022). Rooted in John Dewey's philosophy of progressive education and aligned with constructivist learning theory, DRTA positions teachers as facilitators who guide learners toward autonomy and intrinsic motivation. This active engagement enables students to organize and integrate new knowledge, improve retention, and cultivate lifelong learning habits. Overall, DRTA creates a dynamic learning environment that enhances comprehension, critical inquiry, and independent reading skills (Al Odwan, 2012; Hasan, 2017).

Reading and Writing Skills

A study by Urbano et al. (2021) examined the academic reading and writing skills of Senior High School students in Metro Manila through a comprehensive needs analysis that combined surveys, diagnostic assessments, and interviews with teachers and learners. Findings revealed that students struggled with identifying text development patterns, evaluating coherence, applying grammar accurately, and expanding vocabulary, all of which hindered reading comprehension. In writing, difficulties included limited background knowledge, weak citation practices, and challenges in grammar and vocabulary, resulting in inconsistent expression and varied writing patterns. To address these issues, the study recommended explicit instruction in reading and writing strategies, a text-based approach to strengthen understanding of structure and coherence, and collaborative tasks to promote peer learning and build confidence in academic literacy. The reviewed literature highlights the multidimensional nature of reading comprehension, encompassing both literal understanding of explicit information and inferential interpretation of implicit meanings. Traditional strategies, while once effective, appear less suited to modern learners who increasingly engage with digital texts, underscoring the need for approaches that foster active participation and deeper engagement. The Directed Reading Activity (DRA) has been shown to enhance comprehension through engagement, deep reading, and reflective practices, though it often requires extensive teacher involvement. In contrast, the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) emphasizes prediction, inquiry, and independent learning, encouraging students to critically analyze texts and develop confidence in their comprehension skills. Rooted in Dewey's philosophy of meaningful learning, DRTA positions teachers as facilitators and promotes retention through active exploration. Studies conducted in the Philippine context, such as Urbano et al., revealed persistent challenges in reading and writing skills among Senior High School students, including difficulties in recognizing text structures, evaluating arguments, and addressing vocabulary and grammar limitations. While explicit instruction was recommended, concerns were raised about its potential to limit creativity. Comparative analyses of international and local studies consistently emphasized the importance of active engagement and interactive reading strategies yet highlighted a gap in research on reading engagement within the Philippine setting. This study addresses that gap by focusing on Grade 11 students' independent learning, exploring how DRTA can enhance comprehension and foster autonomy in their academic development.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative approach using a quasi-experimental non-equivalent group pretest-post-test design. The participants were 60 Grade 11 students enrolled in Reading and Writing Skills at Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School, divided into two classes. The HUMSS-A class served as the experimental group, receiving instruction through the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA), while the HUMSS-B class functioned as the control group and was taught using direct instruction. This design allowed for the comparison of reading comprehension outcomes between students exposed to DRTA and those taught through traditional methods.

Sampling Design

This study employed purposive sampling to select participants from two Grade 11 classes, HUMSS-A and HUMSS-B, at Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School. Purposive sampling, a non-probability technique,

was used to deliberately identify students most aligned with the study’s objectives. The Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand was chosen because it emphasizes communication, critical thinking, and analytical skills, making its students suitable for evaluating the effectiveness of the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA). This targeted approach ensured that the data collected was directly relevant to the research focus and enriched the validity of the findings.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School, located in Barangay Veterans Village, Project 7, Quezon City. This site was selected for accessibility to the participants and relevance to the research objectives, as the respondents were enrolled in Reading and Writing Skills during the second grading period of School Year 2025–2026. The locale provided an appropriate setting to analyze differences in pre-test and post-test scores between the experimental and control groups.

Research Participants

The participants consisted of 60 Grade 11 Senior High School students from two classes of Reading and Writing Skills at Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School. The HUMSS-A class served as the experimental group, while HUMSS-B functioned as the control group. Students were selected through purposive sampling to ensure alignment with the study’s focus on evaluating the efficacy of the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) in improving reading comprehension.

Research Instrument

The primary research instrument used in this study was a 30-item multiple-choice Reading Comprehension Test developed based on the Reading and Writing Skills Curriculum Guide and constructed following a table of specifications. The test measured four cognitive domains of learning: remembering, understanding, applying, and analyzing. It was administered as both a pre-test and post-test to two Grade 11 classes, HUMSS-A and HUMSS-B. The experimental group (HUMSS-A) received instruction through the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) prior to the post-test, while the control group (HUMSS-B) was taught using direct instruction.

Data Gathering Procedure

Quantitative data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage distribution were employed to describe student achievement, while paired t-tests were used to determine significant differences between pre-test and post-test scores in both experimental and control groups. The study was conducted during two sessions for each class. In the experimental group (HUMSS-A), students completed a pre-test followed by instruction using the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA), which involved prediction, exploration, and reflection activities. In the control group (HUMSS-B), students also completed a pre-test and were taught through direct instruction using the Directed Reading Activity (DRA), which included apperception, reading, discussion, and post-reading assessment. Both groups concluded with a post-test to measure comprehension outcomes.

Results and Discussions

Problem 1: What is the average of the following scores of the participants in terms of Pre-Test Scores of the Control Group, Post-Test Scores of the Control Group, Pre-Test Scores of the Experimental Group and Post-Test Scores of the Experimental Group?

Table 1: T-Test - Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Exp_Pre	17.77	30	5.167	.943
Exp_Post	19.37	30	5.075	.927
Pair 2 Control_Pre	17.77	30	4.384	.800
Control_Post	17.77	30	7.808	1.426

Table 1 shows the paired samples statistics comparing the pre-test and post-test scores of both the experimental and control groups. The experimental group (HUMSS-A) demonstrated an increase in mean score from 17.77 (SD = 5.167) to 19.37 (SD = 5.075), indicating an improvement in reading comprehension following the implementation of the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA), while the control group (HUMSS-B) maintained the same mean score of 17.77, despite an increase in variability (SD = 4.384 to 7.808), suggesting inconsistent performance with no overall gain. Since both groups started with identical pre-test means, baseline equivalence was established; however, only the experimental group showed measurable progress, highlighting the potential effectiveness of DRTA as an instructional strategy. This finding is supported by studies such as Fitriyani et al. (2020), which found that DRTA significantly enhances students’ reading comprehension by promoting active engagement and prediction, and Utami and Sugirin

(2019), who reported that DRTA improves learners' critical thinking and comprehension through interactive reading processes.

Problem 2: Is there a significant difference in the Pre-Test Scores of the Control Group and the Experimental Group?

Table 2: T-Test - One-Sample Statistics (Pre-Test)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Control_Pre	30	17.77	4.384	.800
Exp_Post	30	17.17	5.167	.943

Table 2 shows the comparison of pre-test scores between the control and experimental groups. The control group obtained a mean score of 17.77 (SD = 4.384), while the experimental group recorded a slightly lower mean of 17.17 (SD = 5.167), indicating minimal difference in their initial reading comprehension levels. The relatively close mean scores and comparable standard deviations suggest that both groups possessed similar abilities prior to the intervention, establishing baseline equivalence. This is important in quasi-experimental research, as it ensures that any changes observed in the post-test can be more confidently attributed to the instructional treatment rather than pre-existing differences. This finding is supported by Creswell (2014), who emphasized that establishing group equivalence at baseline strengthens internal validity in experimental studies, and Fraenkel, Wallen, and Hyun (2012), who noted that comparable pre-test results are essential in determining the true effect of an intervention.

Problem 3: Is there a significant difference in the Post-Test Scores of the Control Group and the Experimental Group?

Table 3: T-Test - One-Sample Statistics (Post Test)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Control_Post	30	17.17	7.808	1.426
Exp_Post	30	19.37	5.075	.927

Table 3 shows the comparison of post-test scores between the control and experimental groups. The experimental group obtained a higher mean score (M = 19.37, SD = 5.075) compared to the control group (M = 17.17, SD = 7.808), indicating a positive trend in favor of the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA). However, despite this observed difference, the statistical analysis revealed no significant difference between the two groups, suggesting that the improvement in the experimental group was not strong enough to be considered statistically distinct from the control group's performance. The relatively higher standard deviation in the control group further indicates greater variability in scores, which may have influenced the results. The absence of statistical significance may be attributed to factors such as small sample size, short duration of intervention, and individual differences among learners. This finding is supported by Gravetter and Wallnau (2021), who emphasized that small sample sizes and high variability can reduce the likelihood of detecting significant differences, and Pallant (2020), who noted that insufficient exposure to an intervention may limit its measurable impact.

Problem 4: Is there a significant difference in the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Control Group?

Table 4: T-Test – Paired Differences Samples Test

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Exp_Pre Exp_Post	-2.200	1.972	.360
Pair 2 Control_Pre Control_Post	.600	5.512	1.006

Table 4 shows the paired differences between the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group. The results indicate a minimal mean difference of 0.60 (SD = 5.512), reflecting a negligible change in students' performance from pre-test to post-test. This suggests that the control group's reading comprehension remained relatively stable over the intervention period, with no meaningful improvement observed following the use of direct instruction. The relatively large standard deviation further implies variability in individual scores, indicating that any minor changes were inconsistent across participants and did not contribute to a significant overall gain. These findings suggest that the traditional instructional approach may not be sufficient to produce measurable improvements in reading comprehension within a limited timeframe. This is supported by Hattie (2009), who emphasized that passive instructional methods tend to yield lower effect sizes compared to interactive strategies, and Marzano (2007), who highlighted that effective learning requires active engagement and structured strategies to significantly influence student achievement.

Problem 5: Is there a significant difference in the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Experimental Group?

Table 5: T-Test – Paired Differences Samples Test

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Exp_Pre Exp_Post	-2.200	1.972	.360
Pair 2 Control_Pre Control_Post	.600	5.512	1.006

Table 5 shows the paired differences between the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group. The results reveal a mean difference of -2.200 ($SD = 1.972$), indicating a notable increase in post-test scores compared to pre-test performance, which reflects a significant improvement in students' reading comprehension after the implementation of the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA). The relatively low standard deviation suggests that the improvement was consistent across participants, indicating that the intervention had a stable and positive effect on most students. This finding confirms that DRTA is an effective instructional strategy in enhancing reading comprehension by promoting active engagement, prediction, and critical thinking during reading tasks. In contrast, the control group showed minimal change, reinforcing the impact of the intervention. This result is supported by Al Odwan (2012), who found that DRTA significantly improves students' comprehension through active involvement in the reading process, and Hasan (2017), who reported that DRTA enhances learners' ability to analyze and understand texts effectively.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established ethical principles in conducting experimental research. Prior to implementation, permission was obtained from the school head, and informed consent was secured from all student participants. The privacy, integrity, and well-being of respondents were prioritized, with identities kept strictly confidential. Measures were taken to protect participants from potential harm, including physical discomfort, emotional stress, or embarrassment. Data were safeguarded against unauthorized access, and findings were reported with accuracy and objectivity. The researcher-maintained transparency and accountability throughout the study to ensure ethical integrity.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) was effective in enhancing the academic performance of students within the experimental group, demonstrating its potential to promote meaningful learning and retention. However, the absence of a statistically significant difference between the experimental and control groups indicates that the intervention's effect did not extend to group-level superiority. This outcome may be attributed to factors such as variability in learner performance, the short duration of implementation, or the limited sample size.

Reccomendations

The findings suggest that the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) can serve as a promising instructional approach when implemented consistently and over an extended period. Teachers are encouraged to integrate its strategies into daily classroom practice to foster deeper comprehension and engagement. Professional development programs should emphasize reflective, evidence-based teaching practices and data-informed instruction to strengthen teacher effectiveness and student outcomes. At the curriculum and policy level, educational leaders may consider adopting similar interventions in areas where student achievement is low, ensuring that implementation is supported by systematic monitoring and evaluation. Finally, future research should employ mixed-method designs to capture both quantitative outcomes and qualitative insights, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing student learning gains.

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